

DEVELOPMENT OF 50CM FLAPPING MICRO AIR VEHICLE AND AUTONOMOUS FLIGHT SYSTEM

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1 General Introduction

Up to recently, the study about Flapping Micro Air Vehicle (FMAV) had been focused on some specific subjects limited to aerodynamic and structural analysis, or miniaturizing mechanical and electric parts of thrust or control system. Because, however, the present study was performed to develop 50cm flapping MAV system which has a capability of fully autonomous flight, it has a wide variety of study fields from the design of whole vehicle structure to the micro autonomous flight control system. The design of 50cm main wing's flapping motion was based on mechanical kinematics and the design of vehicle's whole structure was based on the estimation of aerodynamic and structural parameter. The system identification was performed to estimate the parameter of the vehicle's dynamic equation, and then autonomous flight algorithm including attitude control, altitude control and waypoint guidance was developed. Furthermore, electric hardware such as flight control system (FCS) was developed and integrated into the vehicle, then Ground Control Software and Ground Data Terminal were developed to test and verify autonomous flight performance.

2 Structural Design and Analysis

2.1 Carbon/Epoxy Materials for Wing Structure

The wing structure was composed of carbon / epoxy composite rods and the polycarbonate machining parts to reduce the weight and increase the elasticity. Fig.1. shows the mechanical design of the wing structure, the name and material of each part.

2.2 Flapping Motion Mechanism Design

The flapping motion mechanism was designed for the simple flapping motion with passive twisting motion as shown in Fig.2. It was composed of the gearbox, the brushless DC motor, the single symmetric crank shaft and two connecting rods. To increase the efficiency of wing thrust, the design of gear ratio, crank length, motor KV(RPM/V) was optimized to 17Hz flapping frequency for the cruise flight.

2.3 Flapping Motion Verification in Real Flight

The flapping motion mechanism with the single symmetric crank shaft made a passive twisting motion of wing, which came from wing's structural elasticity. Flapping and twisting motion affected to each other and they were connected strongly to the efficiency of wing thrust. To visualize the phase of flapping and twisting motion in real flight condition and to verify the validity of motion, flight test was recorded with a high speed video camera (1,000 fps) as shown in Fig.3. This kind of verification via high speed video record was very useful to help the design of wing structure with the consideration of three dimensional deformation of wing in real flight condition.

2.4 Flight Performance Test

Flight performance was tested at indoor flight test facility equipped with motion capture camera system, where locates at Air Force Research Laboratory of Wright-Patterson Air Force Base in USA. Fig.4. shows the motion capture system in indoor flight test facility. Time dependent 3D attitude and position data of the vehicle in flight was acquired and logged. Through the investigation of data, a quantitative analysis was carried out for the assessment of

vehicle performance parameters. Fig.5. shows representative example diagram of the data analysis.

3 Aerodynamic Simulation

In this study, flapping MAV operated at low Reynolds number ($10^4 \sim 10^5$) and advance ratio of following equation.

$$J = V / 2b\Phi f \quad (1)$$

where V is free stream velocity, b is wing span, Φ is wing stroke angle, and f is wing flapping frequency. In this flow region, many researchers found that steady-state aerodynamics does not properly capture the physical phenomena and predict forces during flapping motion of wings [1][2]. Furthermore, due to highly flexible wing in an unsteady flow created a difficult aeroelastic analysis, but the flexibility of wings contributed overall thrust and lift [3-5]. And for autonomous flight, the prediction of accurate aerodynamic coefficient is required according to control of the elevator and rudder. Hence, three dimensional unsteady CFD simulations should be carried out though very costly and time consuming works.

3.1 Governing Equation

CFX Version 13, commercial CFD software from ANSYS Corporation, was used for the simulation. CFX could 2-way fluid structure interaction simulation with other commercial software, ANSYS Mechanical. CFX solved the continuity and momentum equation based on finite volume method.

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{U}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho \vec{U})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \vec{U} \otimes \vec{U}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot \tau + S_M = 0 \quad (3)$$

where ρ is the density, \vec{U} is the velocity vector, p is the pressure, S_M is the momentum source and τ is stress tensor which is related to the strain rate by following equation

$$\tau = \mu \left(\nabla \vec{U} + (\nabla \vec{U})^T - \frac{2}{3} \nabla \cdot \vec{U} \right) \quad (4)$$

where μ is kinematic viscosity.

3.2 Grid Generation

For analyzing unsteady flow phenomena due to the flapping motion, the structured grid generated around the wings. The structured grid (hexagonal, prism) is about 30% of total grid (about 3.1M) and other grid is unstructured grid (tetrahedral, pyramid). Because motion of wing changed with time, moving grid mechanism is used by following equation in CFX.

$$\nabla \cdot (\Gamma_{disp} \nabla \delta) = 0 \quad (5)$$

where δ is the displacement relative to the previous mesh locations and Γ_{disp} is the mesh stiffness which determines the degree to which regions of nodes move together. Grid and boundary conditions of this study are shown in Fig.6.

3.3 Numerical Result

Fig.7. shows vortex structure around vehicle when wings are on downstroke, free stream velocity is 5m/s, wing flapping frequency is 18Hz and wing stroke angle is 25deg. The leading edge vortex known as the dominant unsteady aerodynamic mechanism and other physical phenomena can be observed well. The mean and time dependant aerodynamic coefficients during one complete flapping cycle are obtained from analysis. These will be used a six DOF flight simulation.

4 Autonomous Flight System

Autonomous flight system consists of Flight Control System (FCS) in the vehicle, Ground Control Unit (GCU) that Ground Control Software (GCSW) is installed, Control stick and Ground Data Terminal (GDT) as shown in Fig.8.

4.1 Flight Control System

FCS includes various electric parts such as Flight Control Computer (FCC), Attitude and Heading Reference System (AHRS), GPS, modem, micro camera, video transmitter, motor and etc. And all of

them were integrated into the fuselage of the vehicle. Fig.9. shows FCS hardware fully integrated into the vehicle.

4.1.1 MEMS Inertial Sensor Choice for AHRS

In the field of micro UAV system, typically, IMU that MEMS sensors integrated is used for AHRS to reduce the weight. But, MEMS accelerometer and gyroscope sensor are known to have a critical bias in the status of vibration. Especially, flapping MAV has no choice but to make a strong vibration that comes from flapping motion, therefore MEMS sensor should be chosen carefully after sensor level's vibration test. In this study, 4 accelerometer models(ADXL345/ADIS16240/16405/16223; ADI) were tested in a certain vibration condition, which was set to the wave of 17Hz and 15mm amplitude (p-p). This vibration condition is same to real cruise flight condition and it was attained from the result of indoor flight test with motion capture system at AFRL in USA. Fig.10. shows the results of the vibration frequency and amplitude analysis of the fuselage at cruise flight mode in indoor flight test. The blue curve shows the vibration amplitude of fuselage on z axis. And the red curve of main wing's flapping motion was drawn for the reference. As shown in Fig.11., an each accelerometer was mounted on the shaker (TV51075-M) and accurate fuselage vibration mentioned above was reproduced and controlled by LabVIEW software. Fig.12. shows how much the ADXL345 accelerometer's output data would be biased after low pass filtering (Bartlett Window FIR filter) in the vibration (red curve was drawn to find the bias easily). Similar phenomenon was also observed on another accelerometer models, but as shown in Fig.13., ADIS16405 model's bias was the smallest especially. Finally, therefore, ADIS16405 which has 3-axis gyroscope and magnetometer as well as accelerometer was chosen as IMU to develop AHRS.

4.1.2 AHRS aiding by GPS

Traditional stand-alone AHRS based on MEMS sensor had been embedded with accelerometer, gyroscope, and magnetometer. Attitude and heading had been estimated by data fusion from these 3 different kinds of sensors. But traditional AHRS couldn't estimate the attitude information accurately if it is exposed to long-time acceleration flight such as small radius circular turning. Furthermore,

flapping MAV can have more acceleration flight condition which comes from the environmental effect even such as a mild wind, because it is very light and it has a small thrust. In this study, therefore, GPS velocity information was coupled with AHRS to measure pure gravity after eliminating acceleration flight effect. And extended Kalman filter was designed for data fusion of various kinds of sensors such as barometer as well as GPS. Table 1. shows all sensors used to develop AHRS aiding by GPS.

4.1.3 FCS Mainboard

DSP was used for flight control computer (FCC). And AHRS, GPS, modem (data up and down link) were integrated together on FCS mainboard to minimize the weight. Flight control computer gets all sensor data from peripheral devices and then estimates all navigation information including the attitude, the heading and the position via extended Kalman filter. Based on this navigation information, it runs autonomous flight guidance and control algorithm. Finally, FCC outputs a PWM signal to servo motor linked to the control surface as well as the electric speed controller connected to main motor. In addition, FCC communicates with GCS (Ground Control System) via data modem. And FCC can setup the video transmitter's frequency channel from the user command. Table 1. shows all electric devices fully integrated on FCS mainboard and it shows the weight of an each part and the total weight of FCS.

4.1.4 Video Transmitter and Camera

To wireless-transmit the video, Micro 5.8GHz video transmitter RF module was developed. To reduce the weight, high efficient FSK modulation scheme was applied to RF module. Fig.14. shows the system block diagram of video transmitter. Micro camera is equipped as forward looking camera at a front of the fuselage, which is pinhole camera based on 1/4" CMOS sensor

4.2 Ground Control System

GCS consists of GCU, GCSW, Control stick and GDT. GCSW runs in GCU and it processes various data received from FCS via GDT then, it sends command data to FCS via GDT. Bluetooth data modem and video receiver is integrated into GDT. Rugged laptop computer (ToughbookTM, Panasonic)

was used as GCU. GCU is connected to GDT through USB and RS-232 interface wire-harness.

5 Autonomous Flight Control Algorithm

5.1 6 DOF Dynamic Model

A six DOF dynamic model is constructed for flapping MAV. The dynamic equations of motion consist of three equations of translational motion and another three equations of rotational motion around the center of mass of the vehicle. These equations can be expressed as Equation (6) and (7).

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{u} \\ \dot{v} \\ \dot{w} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X/m \\ Y/m \\ Z/m \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -r & q \\ r & 0 & -p \\ -q & p & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} u \\ v \\ w \end{bmatrix} \quad (6)$$

$$\begin{bmatrix} \dot{p} \\ \dot{q} \\ \dot{r} \end{bmatrix} = [I]^{-1} \left(\begin{bmatrix} L \\ M \\ N \end{bmatrix} - \begin{bmatrix} 0 & -r & q \\ r & 0 & -p \\ -q & p & 0 \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} p \\ q \\ r \end{bmatrix} \right) \quad (7)$$

Where u , v , and w are the translational velocity components resolved in the body frame; p , q , and r are the components of angular velocity vector expressed in the body frame; m is the mass of the fuselage; $[I]$ is the inertia matrix about the body axis. The applied forces X , Y , and Z are given by Equation (8) and sum of the two external forces: the aerodynamic forces, the body damping forces and the gravity force.

$$\begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix}_a + \begin{bmatrix} X \\ Y \\ Z \end{bmatrix}_g \quad (8)$$

The applied moments L , M , and N in the body frame are given by Equation (9) and contain contributions from the steady and the unsteady aerodynamic moment. The unsteady aerodynamic moment provides a damping source for angular motion. The nonlinear 6-DOF flight simulation model is built in the MATLAB[®] and Simulink[®] environment for testing and simulation purposes.

$$\begin{bmatrix} L \\ M \\ N \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} L \\ M \\ N \end{bmatrix}_a + \begin{bmatrix} L \\ M \\ N \end{bmatrix}_{ua} \quad (9)$$

5.2 Autopilot Design

Autopilots are implemented to control the flapping MAV, and they are classified into three controllers: pitch control, yaw/roll control, and altitude control. As Fig.15. shows, the autopilots take guidance commands from waypoint guidance and output the commanded deflection angles that should be required in order to control the vehicle. Pitch control loop, which compute the elevator deflection angle, is to ensure that the pitch angle of the vehicle tracks the pitch command angle. The command is determined by Proportional-Integral-Derivative (PID) controller.

$$\delta_e = K_{P,\theta}(\theta_c - \theta) + K_{I,\theta} \int (\theta_c - \theta) dt + K_{D,\theta} \dot{\theta} \quad (10)$$

Both aileron and rudder control input are used together to turn a conventional aircraft, but our flapping MAV uses rudder alone.

$$\delta_r = K_{P,\phi}(\phi_c - \phi) + K_{I,\phi} \int (\phi_c - \phi) dt + K_{D,\phi} \dot{\phi} \quad (11)$$

The altitude of a flapping MAV can be maintained by an altitude hold autopilot. Basically the altitude hold autopilot, which computes the throttle actuator position command, is constructed to minimize the deviation between the actual altitude and the desired altitude.

$$\delta_t = K_{P,h}(h_c - h) + K_{I,h} \int (h_c - h) dt + K_{D,h} \dot{h} \quad (12)$$

6 Conclusion

In this paper, 50cm flapping micro air vehicle and autonomous flight control system were developed. Wing structure and flapping motion mechanism were designed. And the motion in real flight was verified via high speed video camera. Flight performance was measured at AFRL's indoor flight facility. And CFD aerodynamic analysis was tried for an aerodynamic simulation. Regarding autonomous flight system, FCS, GDT and GCSW were developed and integrated. Finally, based on 6

DOF dynamic model equations, autonomous flight control algorithm was developed.

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Fig.1. Mechanical design of main wing

Fig.2. Design of flapping motion mechanism

Fig.3. Flapping and twisting motion (1,000 fps)

Fig.4. MAV indoor flight test facility (AFRL, USA)

Fig.5. Example diagram of flight data analysis

Fig.6. Isometric view of computational domain

Fig.7. Vortex structure at down-stroke

Fig.8. Configuration of flapping MAV system

Fig.9. FCS fully integrated into the vehicle

Table 1. Electric devices fully integrated on FCS

Type	Feature	Weight	
FCC	DSP (CPU)	1g	
Modem	2.4GHz Bluetooth	1g	
Video TX	5.8GHz FSK Modulation	5g	
Camera	Pinhole 1/4" CMOS	1g	
Tacho	Hall sensor	0.5g	
A	Acc		
H	Gyro	ADIS16405 (MEMS IMU)	7.0g
R	Mag		
S	Baro	Atmospheric pressure	0.1g
w/	GPS	Chipset w/ Ext. Antenna	7g

Fig.10. Vibration frequency and amplitude analysis

Fig.14. System block diagram of video transmitter

Fig.11. Vibration test for MEMS accelerometer

Fig.15. Autonomous Flight Control Structure

Fig.12. ADXL345 accelerometer's bias after LPF

Fig.13. ADIS16405 accelerometer's bias after LPF

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